

[Other logos may be entered – e.g., Research Centre]

EXAMPLE OF INFORMED CONSENT

(example to be adapted according to the circumstances of the study, **for studies where data is collected from the participants**, pursuant to Article 13 of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR); if data has not been obtained from the participant, add information about the origin and categories of personal data collected, including, if applicable, whether it came from sources accessible to the public, pursuant to Article 14 of the GDPR)

This study is part of a research project taking place at **Iscte – Instituto Universitário de Lisboa**, (if funded, indicate the entity and respective references).

The study aims to _____ (succinctly and clearly describe the aim). Your participation in the study, which is highly valued as it will contribute to the advancement of knowledge in this field of science, consists of _____ (succinctly and clearly describe the type and duration of the tasks to be carried out by the participant).

Iscte is the controller of your personal data that are collected and processed exclusively for the purposes of the study, legally based on _____ (indicate Article 6(a) and/or Article 9(2)(a) of the General Data Protection Regulation, as applicable).

The study is conducted by _____ (indicate the name of the investigator and her/his e-mail), who you may contact to clear up any doubts, share comments or exercise your rights in relation to the processing of your personal data. You may use the contact indicated above to request access, rectification, erasure or limitation of the processing of your personal data.

Your participation in this study is **confidential**. Your personal data will always be processed by authorised personnel bound to the duty of secrecy and confidentiality. Iscte assures the use of appropriate techniques, organisational and security measures to protect personal information. All investigators are required to keep all personal data confidential.

In addition to being confidential, participation in the study is strictly **voluntary**: you may choose freely whether to participate or not. If you have decided to participate, you may stop your participation and withdraw your consent to the processing of your personal data at any time, without having to provide any justification. The withdrawal of consent shall not affect the lawfulness of processing based on consent before its withdrawal

Your personal data will be kept for _____ (*specify the time, criteria or moment of the study when the data will be anonymised or destroyed*), after which they will be destroyed or anonymised, with their anonymity being assured in the study's results, being disclosed only for purposes of statistics, teaching, communication in scientific meetings, books or articles.

There are no expected significant risks associated with participation in the study (*if they do exist, indicate what they are and which measures have been taken to mitigate/control their effects*). Iscte does not disclose, or share with third parties, information related to its personal data. (*if data is processed by third-parties on behalf of Iscte (outsourcing) or there is intention of sharing data with other research teams or studies, add: In some cases, the research team may share data with other research teams, or even service providers acting under our supervision and responsibility. In this study, personal data are disclosed to the following entities:*

- *identify investigator / research team / or service provider*).

(if personal data are transferred to a third country or to an international organisation outside the European Economic Area, include that information and note the existence, or not, of a 'adequacy decision' by the Commission; if there is no 'adequacy decision' for that country, information should be included on the risks that could arise to the participants and the measures taken to mitigate them)

(if the personal data processing involves automated individual decision-making, including profiling, referred to in Article 22(1) and (4) of the GDPR, include useful information concerning the underlying logic, as well as the importance and foreseen consequences of this processing for the participant).

Iscte has a Data Protection Officer who may be contacted by e-mail: dpo@iscte-iul.pt. If you consider this necessary, you also have the right to submit a complaint to the Portuguese Data Protection Authority (CNDP).

I declare that I have understood the aims of what was proposed to me, as explained by the investigator, that I was given the opportunity to ask any questions about this study and received a clarifying reply to all such questions. **I accept** participating in the study and consent to my personal data being used in accordance with the information that was given to me.

Yes No

_____ (place), ____/____/____ (date)

Name: _____

Signature: _____

(IF THE ACTUAL PARTICIPANT DOES NOT SIGN DUE TO AGE OR INABILITY (see Articles 7 - “Minor participants” and 8 - “Adult participants who are unable to provide informed consent” of Law 21/2014 of 16 April; also, see Article 14 of the GDPR;)

(minors who are able to understand should also sign the document, expressing their assent)

Name: _____

Identification Document number: _____

Date or expiry: ____/____/____

Legal representative: _____

(if a relative, indicate the degree of kinship, bearing in mind that the authorisation must be signed by the legal representative, who might not be one of the parents or another relative)

Signature: _____